

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Constructing a Millitome and Generating Virtual Tissue Blocks

Preparing organ models for use with millitomes

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Introduction

A millitome (from Latin mille, meaning “thousand,” as in millimeter, and the Greek *temnein*, meaning “to cut”) is a device designed to hold a freshly procured organ and facilitate cutting it into many small tissue blocks of well defined size and shape for usage in single cell analysis. A millitome has discrete equally placed cutting grooves in both the x and y directions to guide a carbon steel cutting knife to produce uniformly sized tissue blocks that match the shape and size of organs from the 3D Reference Object library (Browne et al. 2021) (HuBMAP Consortium 2022). The procedures outlined in this Standard Operating Procedure describe how to generate millitomes and how to ensure that spatial locations for each slice or cube are retained in the Human Reference Atlas (Börner et al. 2021). This Standard Operating Procedure is designed to capture the general procedures for constructing a millitome, and assumes a base level of familiarity with 3D modeling software. Those interested more generally in how millitomes are created may also find this SOP of interest.

The millitome 3D model has two main uses:

1. Provide 3D geometry data which can be 3D printed as a physical millitome so whole human organs can be systematically cut into many tissue blocks.
2. Provide 3D data for tissue blocks cut with a millitome. This 3D data can then be used in a web interface like the Exploration User Interface (EUI, <https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/ccf-eui>) or another virtual environment such as the HuBMAP Organ Gallery (<https://osf.io/z9gm3>).

Using the same 3D geometry for both purposes guarantees that dimensions, proportions, and other attributes of a specific millitome match in both the physical and virtual versions.

To learn more about using a millitome, please read the accompanying SOP titled [Using a Millitome](#).

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Roles and Responsibilities

The **Millitome Modeler** creates millitome files that can be 3D printed. They also generate matching 3D virtual tissue blocks for use in the Exploration User Interface and other tools.

Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Role	Name	Email
Millitome Modeler	Peter Kienle	pmkienle@iu.edu

Procedures

Overview

The exact properties and dimensions of a millitome 3D object are based on organ models from the [CCF HubMAP 3D Reference Object Library](#).

The millitome modeler uses [OpenSCAD](#), an open-source, code-based 3D modeler, to create the 3D geometry. The 3D files are then exported in STL format (“STL Files Explained | Learn about the STL File Format | Adobe” 2023) and imported into a 3D printing application such as [Ultimaker Cura](#) or [MatterControl](#). To view the exported STL files, an extra step in 3D modeling software such as [Blender](#), [Maya](#) or [Cinema 4D](#) is necessary to apply materials and textures to the 3D model. It can then be rendered and exported in a web-friendly file format.

Fig. 1 3D-printed millitome with tissue block IDs (left). Matching virtual 3D blocks (right)

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Preparing the Organ Model

All millitome models use 3D reference organs from the NLM Visible Human Project (Ackerman 1998; Spitzer et al. 1996) available via the [HRA Portal](#).

The following sections describe how to prepare a fully closed 3D mesh of a 3D reference organ's outer shell and export it to be used as a mold for a millitome. The instructions follow a workflow using Cinema 4D (C4D).

Dimensions are in cm; VH_F_left_kidney

The source model of this kidney has a few structures on the inside. In order to use the organ model for a boolean operation, which cuts a mold out of a 3d box primitive, these inner structures need to be removed, so that only a single, completely closed shell remains.

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Left to right: Box object (A); Kidney model (B) placed in box; “Subtract B from A” boolean operation creates the mold cutout

Editing the Organ Model

The [source kidney model](#) is downloaded in GLB format. Since Cinema 4D does not import GLB files, Blender is used to convert the file to FBX format. The converted file can then be opened in Cinema 4D.

Selective hiding of mesh objects and visual inspection is used to determine which structures belong to the outer shell and which ones are on the inside. (Fig.1)

Fig. 1 Left: Hierarchy of all mesh objects in original model; Right: VHF_F_kidney_capsule_L is the outer shell.

The capsule structure is the only mesh needed. Everything else can be deleted.

The kidney source model comes with an axis origin that is outside of the organ mesh.

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The editing process will be much easier if the axis origin of the source object is at the center of the 3D mesh (C4D: Tools->Axis->Axis Center), see Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 Left: Axis origin of source object; Right: Axis origin has been centered inside mesh.

Confirm that there is an inner shell (Fig. 3).

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Fig. 3 Zooming “into” the structure reveals an inner shell.

The inner and outer shells of this object are part of a single mesh. All points and polygons of the inner shell need to be deleted.

Individual points along the rim of the opening are selected to create a seam of selected points. This results in a continuous loop all around the opening (Fig. 4).

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Fig. 4 A seam of individual selected points around the opening.

These points are deleted to detach the inner from the outer shell. All points on the inner shell can now be selected (C4D: Select->Select Connected). See Fig. 5.

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Fig. 5 All points on the inner shell are now selected.

All selected points are deleted, which should remove the complete inner shell (Fig. 6).

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Fig. 6 Stray polygons must be deleted manually.

Any unused points are removed (C4D: Mesh->Remove->Optimize...). See Fig. 7.

Fig. 7 Optimize mesh is used to remove any stray points.

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The opening in the shell mesh must be closed (C4D:Mesh->Add->Close Polygon Hole). In Polygons mode, all polygons are selected and their normals are aligned (C4D:Mesh->Normals->Align Normals). See Fig. 8.

Fig. 8 Closed polygon hole and aligned normals (short white vectors pointing away from the polygons).

Organ models from the HuBMAP repository are positioned relative to a common scene origin (Fig. 9).

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Fig. 9 Location of left male kidney relative to scene origin.

To use an organ model for millitome creation in OpenSCAD, it needs to be moved and rotated so that it lines up with the 3D box used for the millitome production process. Millitome geometry created in OpenSCAD is oriented so that the top/left corner point is at position 0/0 and lies flat, aligned on the X/Z plane. This is necessary for a successful 3D print. The kidney model has to be moved to that position, and aligned and rotated as required.

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Fig. 10 Kidney model has to be moved and rotated to make the mold cutout.

The edited kidney model is translated to the scene origin (PX, PY, PZ = 0). See Fig. 11.

Fig. 11 Kidney model has been translated to X, Y, Z = 0.

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Then the object needs to be rotated, so that it will align with the box 3D object in OpenSCAD, where the mold is cut out (Fig. 12).

Fig. 12 Left: This model needs to be better aligned to the X and Z axis; Right: After correction using the rotation tool.

The next few steps will be easier after switching Viewport Display mode to Box, to show only the bounding box of the organ mesh. The organ model's bounding box is centered at the scene origin. The Enable Axis tool is used in Top View to move the origin axis precisely to the top/left corner of the bounding box. After the Enable Axis tool has been turned off, each of the model's X, Y, Z coordinates are reset to zero one more time.

The top/left corner of the bounding box is now at the scene's origin (Fig. 13).

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Fig. 13 Left: Center of bounding box; Center: Object axis aligned to top/left of bounding box; Right: Object axis reset to scene origin.

To successfully create a millitome, OpenSCAD not only needs an edited and aligned STL model of the organ, but also the dimensions of that organ model. A custom XPresso script called [Organ Placement](#) is used to measure the organ model.

The script file is merged into the currently open kidney editing session (C4D: File->Merge Project). See Fig. 14.

Fig. 14 Organ placing XPresso script has been merged into the session.

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The XPresso editor is opened by double-clicking the five small blue dots in the hierarchy list. Then the edited kidney object is dragged to the large rectangle in the top left corner of the editor. Now the XPresso script knows what to measure (Fig. 15).

Fig. 15 Left: Expresso script is waiting for input; Right: After dropping edited kidney object onto object box.

The results are displayed in a HUD (heads-up-display) on the left side in the viewport. The measurement units are in centimeters (Fig. 16).

Fig. 16 Measurements of the bounding box.

These dimensions are added to the [organs.config](#) file, which OpenSCAD depends on to calculate the correct size of the cutting box for each organ.

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Organ models are not symmetrical, and if a whole edited organ model is used as a mold, an unusable 3D printed millitome could be the result. An actual organ sample may not fit through the opening, which is narrower than the space below (Fig. 17).

Fig. 17 Millitome cut box with overhangs.

To prevent these overhanging structures, two “stamps” are created from the edited organ, by extruding the largest cross section to a uniform height.

Two clones of the edited kidney are made and renamed (Fig. 18).

Fig. 18 Left: The whole edited organ; Right: Two identical clones, renamed.

The objects not being worked on are hidden to avoid confusion. In this case a top extrusion is added to the `_bf_0_kidney_I` mesh. This mesh will become the bottom half.

Box selection is used to select the top half of all points of the clone object (Fig. 19).

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Fig. 19 All points in top half selected.

All selected points are deleted (Fig. 20).

Fig. 20 Lower half of the kidney shell remains.

All the points around the top edge of the half shell need to be selected, to be set to a uniform height (Y) in order to produce an even top edge (Fig. 21).

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Fig. 21 All points along the top edge are selected.

All selected points are set to the same Y value (C4D: Mesh->Move->Set Point Value). The goal is to create an extension of the rim about twice as high as the shell. Here, entering 0.03 for Y worked - since this is not a precise value it might take several tries (Fig. 22).

Fig. 22 Uniformly extruded top edge rim.

The bottom shell can now be closed (C4D: Mesh->Add->Close Polygon Hole). See Fig. 23.

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Fig. 23 Close top to get fully closed mesh.

The stamp for the bottom mold is done.

The same process applies to the second clone, except that the lower half of the shell is deleted, while the top half is kept and extruded downwards.

After this process there are three variations of the edited kidney, all occupying the same location in the scene (Fig. 24).

Fig. 24 Left: Whole kidney model; Center: bottom stamp; Right: Top stamp.

The models are exported individually to STL format to a folder called [organs](#).

Generating the Millitome

The modeling process requires a 3D modeling software tool. The preferred tool is OpenSCAD. OpenSCAD is available for Windows and Linux here: <https://openscad.org>. The current millitome version (v1.0) was developed in OpenSCAD 2021.1 on MacOS.

Unlike regular 3D modelers, which rely on a visual point-and-click interface, OpenSCAD is fully code based. That means the 3D geometry is only created after the user executes the text-based

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code. This makes it easy to create variations of a 3D object (e.g., millitomes for different organ sizes or tissue block sizes) by changing relevant parameters in the code.

1. Run the current version of the millitome OpenSCAD code, which is available here: <https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/hra-millitome-generator>
2. Adjust parameters as needed. This OpenSCAD code allows access to several parameters which define the generated 3D geometry:
 - a. Percentage variation of the organ's dimensions (i.e., 100%, 115%, 85%)
 - b. Three tissue block sizing modes:
 - i. cubic block size (i.e., 20x20mm)
 - ii. variable x/y (i.e., 10x20mm, 40x10mm)
 - iii. number of blocks across x/y of organ (block size is calculated)
3. Choose what is included in the STL export file. Due to the scripting nature of OpenSCAD, text commands are used to enable/disable the components and sub-sections of the millitome and the matching block-array. Only enabled components are included in an STL export file. **Fig. 25** and **Fig. 26** show examples.

Fig. 25 Block-array components; exported separately to facilitate texturing

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Fig. 26 Complete millitome geometry for 3D printer, dimensions are in millimeters (left); test print of kidney millitome(right)

A complete set of STL and matching Lookup CSV files for this kidney millitome is available for download [here](#).

References and Resources

- Ackerman, Michael J. 1998. "The Visible Human Project." *Proceedings of the IEEE* 86 (3): 504–11. <https://doi.org/10.1109/5.662875>.
- Börner, Katy, Sarah A. Teichmann, Ellen M. Quardokus, James C. Gee, Kristen Browne, David Osumi-Sutherland, Bruce W. Herr, et al. 2021. "Anatomical Structures, Cell Types and Biomarkers of the Human Reference Atlas." *Nature Cell Biology* 23 (11): 1117–28. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41556-021-00788-6>.
- Browne, K., L. E. Cross, B. W. Herr II, L Record, E Quardokus, A. Bueckle, and K. Börner. 2021. "HuBMAP CCF 3D Reference Object Library." 2021. <https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/ccf/pages/ccf-3d-reference-library.html>.
- Spitzer, V., M. J. Ackerman, A. L. Scherzinger, and D. Whitlock. 1996. "The Visible Human Male: A Technical Report." *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association* 3 (2): 118–30. <https://doi.org/10.1136/jamia.1996.96236280>.
- STL Files Explained | Learn about the STL File Format | Adobe." 2023. 2023. <https://www.adobe.com/creativecloud/file-types/image/vector/stl-file.html>.

FBX Files: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/FBX>

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GBL/gITF Files: <https://docs.fileformat.com/3d/glb/>

Glossary

The below definitions are used in Human Reference Atlas Standard Operating Procedures. When available, definitions were taken from the [HuBMAP Dictionary](#), and aligned with standard terminologies used in relevant fields.

3D printing (or additive manufacturing): The construction of a three-dimensional object from a CAD model or a digital 3D model. The term "3D printing" can refer to a variety of processes in which material is deposited, joined or solidified under computer control to create a three-dimensional object, with material being added together (such as plastics, liquids or powder grains being fused together), typically layer by layer.

Boolean Operation: In a 3D editor two 3D objects can interact in a boolean operation to create a new object, cutting away everything of object A where it intersects with object B (A minus B), or only the area where both objects intersect is kept (A AND B).

Block Array: A set of blocks dissecting the virtual organ sample into a specific, user-requested grid. The individual blocks are arranged in columns and rows, and are separated by cutting slots. Unlike the full millitome, block arrays are only for use in virtual environments.

FBX (Filmbox): A proprietary file format (.fbx) developed by Kaydara and owned by Autodesk since 2006. It is used to provide interoperability between digital content creation applications.

GLB file format: Also called GL Transmission Format Binary file (.glb), this is a 3D file format specification, see <https://docs.fileformat.com/3d/glb/>.

Lookup Table: A tabular mapping of one entity to another, e.g., a phone book (name to number). The millitome lookup table links identification numbers (IDs) in one system (e.g., Millitome IDs) to corresponding identification numbers in another system (HuBMAP IDs).

Millitome: A device used to hold and slice organs into a grid of equally sized tissue blocks. A millitome has an associated digital data package that includes an STL file, a spreadsheet for assigning spatial locations to HuBMAP IDs, and a metadata file with information about the size, dimensions, donor sex, and laterality of the reference organ for which the millitome is fitted.

Organ Mold: This refers to the organ-shaped cavity in the middle of the millitome. It is designed to hold the organ tightly in place while being cut.

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Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs): SOPs are issued to specifically instruct team members in areas of responsibility, procedural steps, appropriate specifications and required records. SOPs outline procedures, which must be followed to support the reproducibility of scientific research. Procedures can take the form of a narrative, a flow chart, a process map, computer screen printouts or combination of all or any other suitable form, however must be written in appropriate, effective grammatical style (e.g., plain English).

STL: STL is a file format commonly used for 3D printing and computer-aided design (CAD). The name STL is an acronym that stands for stereolithography—a popular 3D printing technology. You might also hear it referred to as Standard Triangle Language or Standard Tessellation Language. Each file is made up of a series of linked triangles that describe the surface geometry of a 3D model or object. The more complex the design, the more triangles used, and the higher the resolution (“STL Files Explained | Learn about the STL File Format | Adobe” 2022).

Tissue Block ID: The ID that uniquely identifies a tissue block and links it to the relevant metadata such as donor data. In HuBMAP, this is the Sample ID.

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